

Relationship between yield loss (%) and spikelets diseased with panicle blast (%).

percentage of diseased spikelets with the Asaga scale (see table).

In each plot, 80 hills were harvested to determine grain yield for Mineasahi and rough rice yield for the NILs. Yield loss due to panicle blast was calculated each year from an estimated yield with no

panicle blast for each of Mineasahi and the NILs. The estimated yield with no panicle blast was determined by extrapolating the regression line of yield and percentage of spikelets diseased with panicle blast to the percentage of spikelets diseased with panicle blast with a value of zero.

In each experiment, yield loss was correlated positively with the percentage of spikelets diseased with panicle blast (significant at $P < 0.01$) and the yield loss almost agreed with the percentage of diseased spikelets. However, the agreement between panicle blast and the diseased spikelet percentage and yield loss was not severe compared with the other experiments (see figure).

Yield loss caused by panicle blast varied with the time of *P. grisea* infection on rice panicles and was affected by leaf blast severity. Moreover, weather conditions and cultivar resistance may affect yield loss. However, our results show that yield loss due to panicle blast can be estimated by the percentage of diseased spikelets under severe disease conditions. The method is very simple and the percentage of diseased spikelets in rice hills can also be assessed directly without the Asaga scale. Farmers who cultivate rice under severe panicle blast conditions can use the method to estimate yield losses due to the disease. ■

Inoculation method for rice bunt

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Incidence of rice bunt (kernel smut) caused by *Neovossia horrida* (Tak.) Padwick and Khan is erratic, so screening germplasm for bunt or chemicals for use against bunt under natural incidence is not reliable.

We studied the effect of inoculation method and crop stage on bunt development in a glasshouse in 1993 and 1994. Twenty-five tillers in three replications were inoculated at five growth stages (booting, panicle exertion, anthesis, milk grain, and dough grain). Uninoculated panicles served as the check.

Effect of inoculation method at different stages of growth on rice bunt infection.

Growth stage/method	Bunted grains (%)	
	1993	1994
Boot - syringe	12.00	12.33
	(20.26) ^a	(20.56)
syringe	3.00	3.66
	(9.95)	(11.02)
Panicle exertion - spray	6.67	6.67
	(14.95)	(14.95)
Anthesis - spray	4.00	4.33
	(11.52)	(12.00)
Milk - spray	0.00	0.00
	(0.00)	(0.00)
Dough - spray	0.00	0.00
	(0.00)	(0.00)
Uninoculated check	0.00	0.00
	(0.00)	(0.00)
CD (P = 0.05)	1.10	0.97
CV (%)	7.78	6.63

^a Figures in parentheses are angular transformed values.

Two inoculation methods were used. In the syringe method, 2 ml of sporidial suspension (2500 sporidia ml^{-1}) was injected into the boot. In the spray method, inoculum was sprayed on the panicles. The area enclosing the inoculated plants was covered with muslin cloth; water was sprinkled over the cloth to provide humidity.

At booting, half of the plants were inoculated by syringe method and the other half by spray method. At the other stages, the spray method was used.

The syringe inoculation method resulted in four times more bunted grains than did the spray method (see table). The best stage at which to spray using the spray method was panicle exertion, at which time maximum disease occurrence was recorded. No disease developed when the crop was inoculated after anthesis.

The syringe inoculation method should be adopted for screening germplasm, and the spray method should be used for evaluating antifungal compounds. The syringe inoculation method may not be feasible for inoculating crops on a large scale. ■